

LRO Diviner Compositional Investigation: Highlights and Recent Results. B.T. Greenhagen¹, C.M. Wagoner¹, T.M. Powell¹, R.R. Petersburg¹, and K.L. Donaldson Hanna²; ¹Johns Hopkins Applied Physics Laboratory, ²University of Central Florida, Email: benjamin.greenhagen@jhuapl.edu

Introduction: Owing to fundamental vibrational modes, unique silicate and oxide compositional information is contained in thermal infrared emission. The LRO Diviner Lunar Radiometer is a multispectral radiometer that has observed solar reflectance and thermal emission from the Moon [1]. Operating since July 2009, analyses of Diviner observations have been significantly enhanced through ground truth laboratory experiments as well as improved data processing techniques. This presentation will update the community on the current status of Diviner's compositional investigation, with a focus on results to date and plans moving forward.

Diviner: Diviner has collected the first global, high resolution, multispectral thermal infrared observations of an airless body. Diviner is a nine-channel, pushbroom mapping radiometer that measures broadband reflected solar radiation with two channels, and emitted thermal infrared radiation with seven infrared channels [1]. The three shortest wavelength thermal infrared channels near 8 μm were specifically designed to characterize the mid-infrared Christiansen feature (CF), an emissivity maximum, sensitive to silicate composition [2,3].

Diviner-derived compositional information is generally available in three formats: (1) 'standard' where calibrated radiance is used to derive emissivity [3]; (2) 'normalized-to-equatorial-noon' (NEN) where radiance is empirically normalized to mitigate observed effects of illumination and viewing geometry [4]; and (3) 'space weathering corrected' where the NEN products have been scaled with other datasets to minimize apparent effects of regolith maturity [5]. Each of these products has specific use cases where they are more or less appropriate for analyses, which we will describe.

Data Processing: Diviner effectively acts like 189 discrete radiometers that are co-aligned (21 detectors for each of the 9 wavelengths); however, there are small, well-characterized misalignments between pixels across different spectral channels. Therefore, Diviner data are rigorously processed using ray tracing to ensure radiometrically accurate projection onto a lunar digital terrain model [6]. Because compositional products require ratios of different spectral channels, they historically have required greater numbers of rays (i.e., much longer processing times) than temperature or thermophysical products. Recent testing of an updated process has produced equivalent compositional products with $\sim 7\times$ improvement in processing time, which will facilitate more complex studies with larger (or even global) spatial coverage.

Laboratory Experiments: We are conducting a wide range of laboratory investigations based on experiments with Apollo soils, lunar regolith analogs, and bespoke mineral mixtures with widely varying silicate abundances. Our experiments utilize facilities [e.g., 7, 8] that reproduce surface thermal environments to create appropriate thermal gradients and simulate the wide range of temperatures. The ability to groundtruth Diviner multispectral data with facilities like SABEL (APL), PASCALE (UCF/Oxford), and PARSEC (Stony Brook) provide significant confidence in compositional interpretations.

Predicting In Situ Observations: Diviner observations extend beyond 'typical' nadir pointing (i.e., near-zero emission angle) to include a wide range of illumination and viewing to characterize radiative balance and spectral emission across the full emission phase function (EPF). Thermal models with improved photometric parameters have helped predict the behavior observed by Diviner and can be applied to future surface-based (i.e., high emission angle) thermal infrared observations by payloads such as L-CIRIS, LV-CIRIS, LAFORGE, and AIRES.

Summary: Combining laboratory experiments and Diviner data analysis has provided important constraints on the nature of the lunar surface composition. Advances over the course of the LRO mission have enhanced interpretations using Diviner data. In addition, new orbital and landed datasets with expanded spectral ranges promise to provide even richer datasets with more information about the compositional properties. Lessons learned through Diviner have important implications for the interpretation of these datasets.

References: [1] Paige D.A. et al. (2010) SSR, 150. [2] Logan L.M. et al. (1973) JGR, 78, 4983. [3] Greenhagen B.T. et al. (2010) Science, 329, 1507. [4] Greenhagen B.T. et al. (2011) LPSC, Abstract #1608. [5] Lucey P.L. et al. (2021) JGR Planets, 126, 6. [6] Williams, J.-P. et al. (2016) Icarus, 273, 205-213. [7] Thomas I.R. et al. (2012) Rev.Sci.Inst., 83 (12), 124502. [8] Donaldson Hanna K.L. et al. (2017) Icarus, 283, 326-342.